

Effective Teacher Education Programme for Diversity : Problems, Curriculum and Practices

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Abstract :- Global Human Development Report (HDR, 2004) stated that human development requires more than health, education, a decent standard of living and political freedom. People's cultural identities must be recognized and accommodated by the state, and people must be free to express these identities without being discriminated against in other aspects of their lives. So, multi-cultural aspects and training of human resources are important. Multicultural Education is associated with three things: an idea or concept, an educational reform movement, and a process. For the training of human resources in teacher education components, viz., affirming diversity, leadership, collaboration and partnership must be taken consideration. Curriculum and classroom practices are also important and must be taken enough care keeping in mind multi-cultural aspects.

Key Words :- Teacher Education, Multi-culture, Curriculum and classroom practices.

Introduction :- Human development requires more than health, education, a decent standard of living and political freedom. People's cultural identities must be recognized and accommodated by the state, and people must be free to express these identities without being discriminated against in other aspects of their lives Global HDR (2004). Culture is interrelated and inter connected with human development. Culture can be seen as the sum total of knowledge, opinions, living and food habits, dressing shared by all members of society and transmitted to each other. There is variation of the cultural aspects from state to state and from nation to nation. So multi-cultural

aspects and training of human resources are important.

The primary goal of multicultural education is not merely to promote human relations, to help the students to feel good about them, or to preserve students' native languages and cultures. While these outcomes may be by-products, the primary goal of multicultural education is to promote the education and achievement of all students, particularly those who are traditionally dismissed and underserved in our education system. Nieto (1996) defines multicultural education as antiracist basic education for all students that permeates all areas of schooling, characterized by a commitment to social justice and critical approaches to learning. Furthermore, multicultural education challenges and rejects racism and other forms of discrimination in schools and society. It accepts and affirms differences in race, ethnicity, religion, language, economics, sexual orientation, gender, and other differences that students, communities, and teachers encompass. It should permeate the curriculum and instructional strategies used in schools, as well as interactions among teachers, students, and families in school and outside of it (Nieto, 1999).

Multicultural Education is associated with three things: an idea or concept, an educational reform movement, and a process.

- It incorporates the idea that all students, regardless of their gender, social, ethnic, racial or cultural characteristics, should have an equal opportunity to learn in school.

- It is a reform movement designed to make some major changes in schools and other educational institutions so that students from all social classes, gender, racial, and cultural groups will have an equal opportunity to learn.
- It is an ongoing process whose goals, which include educational equality and improving academic achievement, will never be realized because they are ideals toward which human beings work but never attain.

(Banks, James A., Cherry A. & Mc Gee Banks. (1997)).

CRITICAL COMPONENTS OF AN EFFECTIVE TEACHER EDUCATION FOR DIVERSITY :-

1. **Affirming Diversity:** Melnick and Zeichner (1997) in a research project, entitled "Educating Teachers for Cultural Diversity," highlighted:
 - Hire more new faculty of color in order to diversify their faculty composition.
 - Initiate systematic staff development for teacher education faculty to help them examine their own attitudes about diverse people and learn about various aspects of teacher education for diversity and ways to infuse it into their institutions and programs.
 - The creation of a consortium, where a group of institutions combine their resources to hire staff with expertise in teacher education for diversity to provide part of the teacher education program, usually field experiences and a few courses and seminars related to teaching diverse students. (p. 91)
2. **Leadership:** It is important, therefore, for the leaders of institutions to examine their own beliefs and attitudes about diversity, and encourage other faculty to do so (Zeichner & Melnick, 1998). In other words, change requires leadership, risk-taking, solid planning, and the cultivation of a change-accepting environment. Regarding their initial attitude toward multicultural education Contreras (1988) explains: Teacher educators continue to assume that teacher education students will pick up the necessary knowledge, skills,

and attitudes that will help them teach classes of socio culturally diverse students without any direct instruction and planned experience. Moreover, teacher educators assume that most of the schools will continue to be monoculture and nonsocial: therefore, there is no obligation to commit time and resources to preparing teacher to teach children who are at risk of being miss-educated and undereducated (Contreras, 1988, p. 14).

3. **Collaboration and Partnership:** Preparing university students to teach in twenty-first century classrooms that will be more ethnically and culturally diverse requires a paradigm shift to collaboration among systems relevant to education. Best practices from schools, universities, communities, and industries establish benchmarks that these collaborative systems can be used to develop effective *teacher preparation* programs. When such collaboration exists, the educational systems become aligned in a seamless web of experiences, leading to knowledge, skills, and attitudes inherent in lifelong learning (Patrick & Reinhartz, 1999).

GOALS OF MULTICULTURAL EDUCATION :- Fox & Gay (1995, pp. 71-73) articulate six clusters of objectives of multicultural teacher education at the curriculum level:

- To transmit factual information about ethnic and cultural diversity;
- To train prospective teachers how to aid the personal development of diverse student populations;
- To train prospective teachers how to develop personal empowerment skills in diverse student populations;
- To allow prospective teachers to analyze and clarify their own attitudes and values about cultural diversity;
- To provide prospective teachers with social skills for functioning in diverse educational settings; and
- To train prospective teachers to engage in what they term culturally responsive teaching.

CURRICULUM AND CLASSROOM PRACTICES OF TEACHER PREPARATION PROGRAMME

- Culture foundation knowledge.
- Histories, anthropology, linguistics, psychology, sociology, philosophy, political-economics- all have important perspectives.
- Students need to learn about relates to knowledge of particular culture groups which differ from their own.
- Examine their own culture identity and group patterns is very useful way to begin developing the skills to explore other cultures (Ladson-Billings,1991)
- Autobiographies, fiction, drama, poetry, music, film and about persons of colour provide effective means for knowledge and insight across cultural boundaries (Gay (1977), Green (1993), Jackson).
- Provide experiences to pre-service students with the members of other culture.

Classroom practices :- Judson Hixson describes multi-cultural approach as to instruction requires that teachers learn how to assess and build on the personal, cultural, and social strengths, skills, and competencies that students brings to the classrooms, on their prior knowledge and experiences; that they help students see connections between curricular and content, their current realities, and their future possibilities (1993,10). Thus, culturally responsive teaching is not particular method to be added to a teacher's collective of techniques.

RETHINKING TO ADDRESS PROBLEM OF MULTICULTURAL CLASSROOMS :-

1. **Problem of Instruction :-** There are various instructional strategies and experiences commonly used in teacher education (for example, analysis or preparation of cases, action research projects, teacher research or other forms of practitioner inquiry, technology, construction of portfolios, community immersion, biographical/autobiographical/narrative exploration, micro-teaching, use of videotaped lessons and classroom scenes,

etc.). These strategies would not be effective if they are used by those who ignore the differences between students, are insensitive to cultural diversity, and students' needs. Simply put, the attitudes of educators and teachers need to be examined to validate culturally responsive instruction.

2. **Cultural Immersion :-** The connection between teacher education, school culture, and the social context of communities is central in terms of teaching for change because teacher education reform depends on school reform and school reform depends on teacher education change. The teacher education program needs to be able to provide experiences for prospective teachers that foster a critical perspective to understand and act in relation to families and communities (Grinberg & Goldfarb, 1998). Such experience will provide the future teacher with the possibility of creating meaningful linkages between school, family, and community. Learning about the community's composition and its relationships with schools, both positive and negative, is imperative.

PREREQUISITES OF MULTICULTURAL TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAMS :-

Teacher education programs must prepare all teachers, majority or minority, to provide quality education for all students. Most of the faculty does not have a clear perception about multi culture education. Consequently, many are not comfortable teaching about diversity and culture. Olstad, Foster, and Wyman (1983) indicated that teachers' lacking multicultural education are inadequately prepared for the reality of a pluralistic society and tend to have low expectations for minority children. Teacher educators must ask themselves to what degree their teacher preparation programs (a) facilitate increased cultural self-awareness, (b) cultivate appreciation of diversity, (c) increase cultural competency, and (d) prepare teachers to work effectively with a variety of students and parents, to the extent that education programs achieve these ends, to that extent do they prepare culturally competent teachers? (p. 138).

CONCLUSION :- Human being is influenced by diversity of religion, gender, age related aspects of cultural diversity, group identity, the freedom of thought, conscience and education. Teacher educators must ask themselves about the degree of teacher facilitating increased cultural self-awareness, cultivating appreciation of diversity, increasing cultural competency, and preparing teachers to work effectively with a variety of students and parents, and role of teacher education programme to achieve these ends.

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